

Design & Implementation of Quadratic Boost Converter in Hybrid Renewable System

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Abstract: The paper proposes the design of a quadratic boost converter that provides high voltage gain and efficiency. This converter has been fed with dual input of two renewable sources in parallel that can provide a solution to the issue of reliability related with renewable resources. A comparative analysis has been done on the performance of quadratic boost converter with conventional boost converter which highlights the beneficial advantages of the quadratic boost converter.

Keywords: Quadratic boost, renewable energy sources, hybrid input

1. Introduction

Renewable energies are those sources of energy that can be obtained naturally without depleting the planet's resources. Researchers are developing different technologies to capture and utilize these energies in recent years, making these resources increasingly viable and economical. Renewable energies are a key solution to combating climate change and reducing dependence on fossil fuels [1]. By investing in these energy sources, jobs can be created, and sustainable economic development can be promoted. In summary, renewable energies are a key alternative to ensure a cleaner and safer future for future generations. Hybrid renewable energy systems are those that combine two or more renewable energy sources to generate electricity. These systems are especially useful in places where there is no access to the conventional electrical grid, or where the connection is limited or unstable [2]. The most popular hybrid system combines solar and wind energies. During the day, when the sun shines, solar panels generate electricity that is stored in batteries for later use. At night, when there is no sun, wind energy conversion systems harness the wind to generate additional electricity and charge the batteries [3]. Another example of a hybrid system combines solar and hydro energies. During the day, solar panels generate electricity that is used to pump water from a river or lake to a dam. At night, when there is no sun, the water stored in the dam is released through a hydro turbine to generate additional electricity [4]. Hybrid renewable energy systems can be more efficient and reliable than systems that use a single energy source [5]. Additionally, they allow for a better use of available resources and reduce the cost of generated energy. For these reasons, hybrid systems are becoming increasingly popular worldwide, especially in rural or remote areas [6]-[8].

These hybrid systems, however, require the design of high-gain converters which are compatible with these systems to raise the output voltage, maintaining the efficiency of the system. These converters need a compatible design which can integrate different input sources by aligning them to same voltage level.

Various dc-dc converters can be selected which can integrate more than one renewable source in parallel. This paper provides an analytical comparison between conventional boost converter with modified and cascaded boost converter named as quadratic boost converter.

2. Quadratic Boost Converter

A quadratic boost converter is a type of DC-DC converter that provides a higher voltage gain than a conventional boost converter by combining two boost converter with a single switch. It is particularly useful in applications requiring high step-up voltage, such as renewable energy systems (e.g., photovoltaic panels and fuel cells).

Figure 1. Quadratic Boost Converter

Figure. 1 shows the circuit diagram of a quadratic boost converter.

This project focuses on the design and development of a quadratic boost converter. A quadratic boost converter combines the principles of two conventional boost converters into a single topology using one switch, two inductors, two capacitors, and three diodes [7]. It can achieve a higher output voltage for the same duty cycle compared to a standard boost converter.

- In the on-state, the switch (IGBT) is turned on, D1 and D2 are reverse-biased, whereas D3 is forward-biased. V_{in} and C1 supply currents to inductors L1 and L2, respectively. Thus, the inductor current increases in this model [1].
- In the off state, the switch (IGBT) is turned off, D1 and D2 are forward biased, whereas D3 is reverse biased. Capacitors C1 and C2 get charged through diodes D1 and D2 from the energy stored in inductors L1 and L2, respectively. Thus, the inductor current decreases in this model [1].
- Quadratic boost converter components equations [4]:-

DURING ON DURING OFF

$$L1 = v_{in}$$

$$L1 = v_s - v_{c1}$$

$$L2 = v_{c1}$$

$$L2 = v_{c1} - v_o$$

Now putting volt sec balance

$$L1 = v_{in}(D) + v_{in} - v_{c1}(1 - D) = 0$$

$$v_{c1} = \frac{v_{in}}{1 - D}$$

$$L2 = v_{c1}(D) + v_{c1} - v_o(1 - D) = 0$$

$$v_o = \frac{v_{in}}{(1-D)^2} \text{ (Final output equation of quadratic boost converter)}$$

In Continuous conduction Mode,

DURING ON

DURING OFF

$$L1 = v_L = v_{in}$$

$$L1 = v_L = v_{in} - v_{c1}$$

$$\frac{L_{dil}}{DT} = v_{in}$$

$$\frac{L_{dil}}{DT} = v_{in} - v_{c1}$$

$$\Delta i_l = \frac{v_{in}(D)TS}{L}$$

$$\Delta i_l = v_{in} - \frac{v_{c1}(1 - D)TS}{L}$$

$$\therefore IL = \frac{v_{in}}{R(1-D)^4}$$

$$\therefore L_{min} = \frac{v_{c1}(D)(1-D)^4 r}{2f v_{in}}$$

3. Literature Survey

In paper [9], analysis of three different DC/DC converter topologies i.e. a conventional, a quadratic, and a double cascaded boost converter for a Solar PV system, has been presented. A conventional boost converter may not fulfill the purpose, so cascaded boost converters are employed to overcome this limitation. Cascaded boost converters provide high voltage conversion ratio along with higher efficiency values, in comparison to conventional boost converters.

Authors in paper[10] stated that the application of the high-gain boost DC-DC converter is gaining more attention due to an increasingly wide range of applications for sustainable green energy solutions, as well as other high-voltage applications. A dual voltage boost cell has been developed by incorporating two capacitors in series with two inductors of a conventional quadratic boost converter, and a capacitor was integrated with a second voltage boost cell. The designed converter increases the voltage gain as well as reduces the voltage stress across the switch.

In another paper [11], a high voltage gain modified quadratic boost dc-dc has been proposed, which increases the voltage gain as well as reduces the voltage stress across the switch but when duty cycle increases to 60%, the input current increases, making it less efficient.

4. Comparison of Boost Converter and Quadratic Boost Converter

Boost converter and quadratic boost converters were simulated in MATLAB platform with similar values of design parameters.

Results in terms of efficiency and voltage gain were obtained by varying the input voltage and duty cycle so that an analysis can be done by comparing their outputs.

Table. 1 displays the simulated results of Boost converter at different duty ratio and input voltages.

Table 1. Efficiency and Voltage Gain in Boost Converter at Different Duty Ratio

<i>V_{in}</i> (V)	<i>I_{in}</i> (A)	<i>D</i>	<i>V_{out}</i> (V)	<i>I_{out}</i> (A)	<i>P_{in}</i> (W)	<i>P_{out}</i> (W)	<i>Efficiency</i> (%)	<i>Volt Gain</i>
24	1.318	30	39.61	0.6601	31.632	26.196561	82.6585	34.28
	2.602	50	55.47	0.9244	62.448	51.276468	82.11066	48
	15.86	80	132.7	2.211	380.64	293.3997	77.0806	120
45	2.486	30	74.88	1.248	111.87	93.45024	83.5346	64.285
	4.898	50	104.6	1.743	220.41	182.3178	82.7175	90
	29.78	80	249.4	4.156	1340.1	1036.5064	77.3454	225
60	3.32	30	100.1	1.668	199.2	166.9668	83.8186	85.714
	6.538	50	139.7	2.329	392.68	325.3613	82.9410	120
	10.25	60	173.9	2.899	615	504.1361	81.9733	150
	39.72	80	332.7	5.545	2383.2	1844.8215	77.4094	300

Table 1. shows that boost converter shows a maximum efficiency of 83.8 % for the given set of input parameters.

Table. 2 displays the simulated results of Quadratic Boost converter at different duty ratio and input voltages. It clearly shows an efficiency range of 84 to 95

when the converter is performing within a duty cycle range of 30 to 65 but when the duty cycle is further increased, efficiency reduces significantly.

Table 2. Quadratic Boost Converter Readings

V_{in} (V)	I_{in} (A)	D	V_{out} (V)	I_{out} (A)	P_{in} (W)	P_{out} (W)	$Efficiency$ (%)	$Volt\ Gain$	$\frac{VIN}{(1-D)^2}$ (V)
12	1.019	35	25.49	0.4249	12.228	10.83	88.5672	2.124	28.402
	2.961	50	42.73	0.7122	35.532	30.43	85.6411	3.560	48
	4.397	55	51.86	0.8644	52.76	44.82	84.950	4.321	59.25
	6.827	60	64.45	1.074	81.924	69.219	84.491	5.3708	75
24	2.099	35	53.74	0.8956	50.376	48.129	95.539	2.239	56.80
	6.186	50	88.96	1.483	148.46	131.92	88.858	3.706	96
	14.22	60	134.3	2.239	341.28	300.69	88.106	5.59	150
	39.38	70	205.2	3.419	945.12	701.57	74.230	8.55	266.64
48	8.532	45	152.6	2.543	409.53	388.06	94.75	3.179	158.67
	12.6	50	182.1	3.034	604.8	552.49	91.35	3.793	192
	29.01	60	274	4.567	1392.4	1251.3	89.86	5.708	300
	225.8	80	522.1	8.701	10838.4	4542.7	41.9130	10.877	1200

5. Simulink Model of Quadratic Boost Converter with Hybrid Input Voltages.

Figure. 2 shows the Simulink model of quadratic boost converter with two renewable input voltage sources as solar and wind. The converter operates with good efficiency within a duty cycle range of 35 to 65%.

Figure 2. Hybrid Quadratic Boost Converter

The two renewable sources are kept in parallel with a controlled output which is varied from 8V to 12V to analyse the performance of the hybrid system as shown in Table 3. The maximum efficiency achieved is 94 percent.

Figure 3. Output Waveforms from Hybrid Quadratic Boost Converter

Figure 3. shows the various waveforms of pulse, current through the two inductors, voltage across each inductor each capacitor respectively.

Table 3. Output of the Hybrid Quadratic Boost Converter

V_{in} (V)	I_{in} (A)	D	V_{out} (V)	I_{out} (A)	P_{in} (W)	P_{out} (W)	Efficiency (%)	Volt gain	$\frac{V_{IN}}{(1-D)^2}$ (V)
12	0.8013	30	23	0.3929	9.61	9.036	94.027	1.9166	24.489
11	1.981	45	34.2	0.57	21.791	19.38	88.935	3.109	36.3636
10	2.67	50	38.63	0.6439	26.7	24.87	93.14	3.863	40
8	4.906	60	45.06	0.751	39.248	33.84	86.22	5.63	50

6. Conclusion

The comparative analysis finally highlights that the performance of the quadratic boost converter is better than conventional boost converter in terms of efficiency and voltage gain. However, the converter with the hybrid input works with a high efficiency only within the duty ratio of 40 to 60% beyond which the efficiency reduces. Future work will be related to the practical implementation of the hybrid system.

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